

**FORMING STUDENTS' AESTHETIC ACTIVITY USING APPLIED ART
ELEMENTS IN FINE ARTS LESSONS**

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Abstract: The article talks about the importance of art, visual arts, teaching aesthetic activities in secondary schools through steam training.

Key words: Art, steam training, 3D design, aesthetic culture, types of art, aesthetic activity, applied art elements, national program, decorative arts, child education.

Art is an important process that emerged as a result of the development of the labor process from time immemorial. Due to its introduction into society, human thinking has matured, the sense of beauty has increased, and concepts of real beauty, sophistication, comfort and usefulness have been promoted. The reason for the separation of mental work from physical work was that with the emergence of a class society, great changes took place in social development. This was a great foundation for the development of science and art. It was during this period that artists appeared. Fine art is one of the important factors affecting human life and moral education. The place and role of visual art is incomparable in forming the characteristics of a person to feel beauty and get emotional pleasure from art objects.

One of the important tasks of today's pedagogue is to carry out a number of activities to form and develop the artistic aesthetic taste of general secondary school students. Showing them the famous works of great artists, and even telling the history of the creation of the work, arouses great interest in science in children. For example, to see the beauty of nature in the pictures, the ancient and current life of people, their faith in the bright life to come. they learn. Artistic images have a strong impact on students, they evoke various positive thoughts and feelings. The method of comparing the visual arts of Uzbek and other nations can also be effectively used in the teaching process. It is appropriate for the teacher to draw students' attention to the compositional structure of works of art, the proportion of colors, when conducting conversation classes in the teaching of fine arts. The conversation about the work of fine art should be conducted in the form of question-and-answer and storytelling. The given questions should force students to increase their worldview by perceiving the important side of the content of the artist's work.

Social and economic changes taking place rapidly in the world these days require fundamental reforms in the field of education, bringing educational work up to the level of current requirements. Therefore, in most of the decisions and decrees adopted in our country, special emphasis is placed on the socialization of education - creating a rich aesthetic worldview in students, forming high spirituality, culture and creative thinking in them. Today, the growth of the flow of information and high technical and technological innovations are creating the fourth technological revolution in all aspects of life. As a result, the interests of the individual and the demands of society are changing. STEAM education introduces the integrative approach of education to everyday life with the concepts of scientific research and technical development. Steam is an integration of science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics. The purpose of using this approach in the educational process is to promote scientific literacy and competitiveness by involving the school and the public in ensuring the sustainable development

of the world's development and economy through education. And STEAM education brings robotics, modeling, construction, programming, 3D design and many other innovations to the education system of schoolchildren from all over the world. Study student learning research in the classroom and in extracurricular activities by showing how the knowledge, skills, and competencies imparted in STEAM education are scientifically relevant to everyday life. It is aimed at developing their interest in carrying out, carrying out experiments, developing their creativity focused on designing, and creating news. The connection of STEAM education with visual arts certainly serves to develop children's aesthetic culture.

Art has a positive effect on people's psyche. At the same time, it develops a person's aesthetic culture. Aesthetic culture is a purposeful process of developing an aesthetic attitude of a person to the surrounding reality. The problem of developing the aesthetic culture of students in general secondary schools is one of the main tasks for every pedagogue. The high aesthetic culture of the student helps him to have his own place in the society, the feeling of love for the motherland, and the love of his family and society.

Each subject has its place in child education. Including, the role of visual arts and fine arts in personality formation is that; Through the visual arts, the student gives information about the nature of his mental state, interests, experiences, which no one knows, even those around him, through the colors used by the lines he draws.

Practical art has been developing in our republic since ancient times. Nowadays, the attention to national traditional values is increasing. Elements of applied art used in national costumes are being improved. Love for manual labor has increased. Art has a positive effect on people's psyche. At the same time, it develops a person's aesthetic culture. Aesthetic culture is a purposeful process of developing an aesthetic attitude of a person to the surrounding reality. The problem of developing the aesthetic culture of students in general secondary schools is one of the main tasks for every pedagogue. The high aesthetic culture of the student helps him to have his own place in the society, the feeling of love for the motherland, and the love of his family and society.

And through patterns, unlike all other types of applied art, you can see the close connection of generations, the continuity of traditions. It is because of this continuity that the art of patterning has survived to this day. Artistic painting is the art of creating beauty in the combination of colors and unique compositions. Decorative applied art mainly creates things that serve the needs of everyday life.

The applied decorative art of Uzbekistan, different from the easel image forms, has gone through a complex and multi-century development path in connection with folk art. This type of art is an art aimed at aesthetic perception of reality and creation of innovations. Nowadays, the arts such as fine needlework, carpet weaving, putting flowers on spools, cap sewing, goldsmithing, embroidery, flower embroidery, coppersmithing, pottery, jewelry, and making musical instruments are widespread. The creative style or art style used in horse species is also of great importance. As envisaged in the national program, in the implementation of the tasks set for the formation of the aesthetic consciousness of students, especially visual arts lessons and extracurricular activities are of great importance. Because the role of fine art in the formation and development of human maturity, spiritual and aesthetic taste is incomparable.

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